

**Acknowledgement of Receipt of the Application from the Federal Office of Administration.
by Brian Paul kaess**

"Dear Mr. (Garret) Kaess,
we hope you are well.

We have received confirmation of receipt of the application from the Federal Office of Administration.

The file number is: TSII3-2024 0627 0156-F

Mit freundlichen Grüßen / Kind regards,

Madlin Jolu

.. Paralegal"

Schlun & Elseven Law Firm (Dusseldorf, Germany)

Note: Brian Paul Kaess became aware of this on January 10, 2025.